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Expert Insights: Equity-Centred Survey Methods for Trials in Benin

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Research trials that aim to address critical global health issues, such as iron deficiency among women, must account for gender-based barriers and enablers that influence women’s participation. To better understand how community-based research approaches can reduce barriers to recruitment and participation, we surveyed diverse interest-holders committed to advancing women’s health and equity through gender-specific and -transformative programmes that tackle iron deficiency and poor nutrition. The **purpose** of this knowledge mobilisation activity is to report insights on best practices that ensure trial methods actively support women’s equity and agency to participate in research and health programming that benefits them.

Sample	Experts-by-experience: Beninese women, researchers, graduate students, NGO project managers, youth & community health advocates, economists, and industry impact directors
Phenomenon of interest	Insights and perspectives on conducting equitable research in Beninese communities
Design	Structured survey informed by academic literature and insights from the Alliance Against Iron Deficiency working group to ensure rigor and relevance of the survey questions
Evaluation	Qualitative thematic analysis of surveys to uncover key themes and practical recommendations
Research type	Qualitative, focused on exploring applied and experiential knowledge of experts-by-experience
Outcome	Inform gender-specific research approaches to conduct equitable community-based research

Emerging insights

Overcoming barriers to women’s equitable agency to participate in research trials

Interviews in research trials provide rich quantitative and qualitative data. However, methods that do not account for community-wide cultural and gender norms can create barriers to participation.

Most critical *surveying* methods to ensure women can participate equally:

Local support/peer assistance

Provide assistance through community catalysts or local champions, who can guide participants through the survey process, provide clarity, and ensure women have the resources to participate meaningfully.

Small group interviews

Offer participants the option of small-group survey sessions rather than individual, to increase their comfort and willingness to participate.

Gender- and linguistically-matched interviewer

Empower and train community interviewers who are gender-matched (e.g. women interviewing women) and who can conduct interviews in the participant’s local language.

Visual cues

Use culturally relevant icons, illustrations, etc., to clarify survey questions and response options for participants with low literacy or comprehension.

Key considerations: Identify women’s context-specific barriers and facilitators during trial planning, emphasise and communicate data security and plans to share results with the community!

Best approaches to overcome barriers:

Co-design trial surveys to reflect cultural norms

Facilitate workshop(s) to co-design surveys and a sampling framework with community groups and content experts to ensure surveys reflect social, cultural, and local norms whilst maintaining accuracy.

Iterative training of survey interviewers

Conduct debrief sessions and ongoing booster information sessions to address any arising concerns during the trial and ensure interviewers are fully informed.

Key considerations: Engage local women leaders as catalysts who can encourage participation.

Top strategies to build trust in communities:

Endorsements from local organisations

Engage local partners (community health agents, faith-based organisations, youth and women’s groups, and non-governmental organisations) to endorse the research.

Community sensitisation meetings

Hold separate meetings for women and community leaders, including religious and household leaders, to present the trial’s purpose and benefits, and provide an opportunity to ask questions and raise concerns. Meetings should be led by local organisations and held prior to the start of the trial to best support consent processes and participation.

Key considerations: Provide feedback and present results to communities to build long-term transparency and trust.

Note: actioned approaches may be a blend of recommended strategies